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**REPORT OF A COLLECTIVE INVESTIGATION ON THE
CURETTEMENT OF THE EUSTACHIAN TUBE IN
CHRONIC AURAL SUPPURATION.***

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In presenting for your consideration the procedure suggested by me for the cure of chronic otorrhea, in an article in THE LARYNGOSCOPE of July, 1910, I do so pursuant to a suggestion that I state my present views on this subject.

My own experience since the publication of the article mentioned, has confirmed the views therein expressed; but if a new method of procedure can be carried out only by the originator thereof, it will be of benefit only to the few patients with whom he comes into personal contact; if, on the other hand, the difficulties of technique and general management have been successfully mastered by a sufficient number of other operators in a reasonably large number of cases, the average results obtained by these operators must express the true value of the procedure. Therefore, the experience of others will be of interest and is here presented. In order to ascertain what the experience of other otologists has been with this operation, I have addressed a series of questions to over six thousand otologists in the United States and other parts of the world. Among nearly two thousand replies which I have received, I have found 119 operators who had performed the operation from

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one to fifty-three times, the total number of cases operated upon being 735. This number, both of operators and of cases is, I feel, sufficiently large to warrant statistical deductions, and the interpretation of these figures will be here considered. I wish again to emphasize the fact that the results here reported are not my own, but are the results obtained by other otologists, most of them personally unknown to me, who have derived their knowledge of this procedure from the single article mentioned above. I am entirely satisfied to accept these results as indicating the value of this procedure at the present time, and to stand squarely upon the figures derived from this collective investigation.

Inasmuch as the operation is based upon the principle that the closure of the Eustachian tube is essential to the healing of the diseased ear, it naturally follows that in those cases in which organic atresia did not result from the operation, a cure could not be expected, and the statement that the closure of the tube will be followed by a cure can be true only of those cases in which the tube has actually been closed. However, both sets of figures will be given. Of the 735 cases the tube was successfully closed, after one or more curettings, in 609, or 83 per cent of the cases. The number of patients reported as cured is 379, or 51.5 per cent of the total number, or 62 per cent of the number in which the tube was successfully closed. In other words, more than one-half of all cases of chronic suppuration of the middle-ear have been cured by closing the Eustachian tube through the intact external auditory meatus, and without other surgical treatment. These figures alone are sufficiently high in my estimation to accord to this procedure a permanent place in our practice.

Let us consider therefore the indications and contra-indications for the procedure, as derived from the figures of this investigation. It has been my experience, which I have now confirmed by observations extending over ten years, that it may be stated as a dictum that whenever the Eustachian tube is permanently closed by organic atresia, a perforation in the drum membrane will never close and cannot be made to close. Whenever, therefore, in any case it seems to be possible to restore the continuity of the drum membrane after the suppuration has subsided, and so restore the ear to a perfectly normal condition, the Eustachian tube must not be closed. In such cases the operation is contra-indicated, as it is also in those cases in which it is intended to perform one of the so-called conservative, radical operations, which are also supposed to result in the closure of the drum membrane. Furthermore, the procedure is adapted only for the cure of a chronic suppurative process and should never

be employed in the presence of an acute exacerbation. In like manner, the presence of labyrinthine or intracranial complications demands the immediate exposure of the entire diseased area, and to delay such exposure until the results of tubal atresia can be known would be entirely unjustifiable; besides which, in the presence of intracranial complications, even if these have become latent, any operative procedure upon the ear, short of a radical exposure of the entire diseased area, might be dangerous, as is suggested by the single death which has unfortunately followed this operation. The history of the case was communicated to me as follows:

"Case Orv. S., aged 10. When first seen by me in consultation, September 1st, 1914, the patient, from external appearances, was a very sick youngster. He had a beginning partial paralysis of right arm (sensation not affected) and leg and choreiform movements so marked that it was impossible for him to sit on a chair unsupported. He complained mainly of frontal headaches and discharging left nostril. He could not sleep nights because of the headaches which began three weeks previous and were getting worse. Inspection: Very emaciated and pale with bluish discoloration of lips. Heart beat with terrific force against the anterior chest wall which was slightly bulging over the cardiac area. Left nostril filled with a polypoid mass. This could be very readily seen without lifting tip of nose. Both ears had a slight discharge of aropy character, no odor or discoloration, showing that there was probably no necrosis of bone. Enlarged diseased tonsils and adenoids. Transillumination showed left antrum dark. At this time made a diagnosis of polypoid degeneration of left ethmoid, diseased tonsils and adenoids. The following day he had a slight edema of his hands and feet.

Urine—trace of albumin, otherwise normal.

Blood—Hb. 40 per cent; reds 1,750,000; no differential leucocyte count was made because our regular laboratory man was out of the city. Wassermann at this time seemed to be negative. Heart enlarged downward and outward for about one inch; while he had murmurs at all valves practically, we felt that all his symptoms were due to a toxic absorption from his diseased nose and throat.

Previous History—Measles at three, scarlet at five. Had his tonsils supposedly removed seven times by various men during the last five years.

On account of his desperate physical condition, I decided to tone up his whole system for a week or ten days with rest in bed, etc. Ten days after my first visit I operated at the hospital under ether given by the Gwathmey method. One hour before operation I gave him a hypodermic injection of morphin 1/8 and scopolamin 1/160. Inserted a pharyngeal plug. Removed middle turbinate and ethmoids on left side. Punctured left antrum and washed it out with hydrogen peroxid, 3 per cent, then alcohol, 10 per cent and decinormal sodium chlorid. The antrum simply showed secretion of retention. Nothing pathological in the antrum.

The boy did so well that I removed his tonsils (with snare) and adenoids at the same sitting. Forty-eight hours after operation the swelling of his hands and feet had disappeared; but the thing of greatest interest to us was the complete cessation of all choreiform movements and disappearance of beginning paralysis in the right arm and leg. The boy's heart action and general health improved so that at the end of the third week he began to attend school regularly and took considerable out-door exercise. The discharge from the right ear ceased while that from the left ear gradually grew worse. Treated with alcohol method from middle of October, 1914, until February, 1915. At this time he was no better and the family requested me to do something. I curetted under ether. At this time the boy was practically well, except for this slight ear discharge. The hemorrhage at the time of operation was not considered alarmingly excessive. Convalescence in the hands of the family physician seemed to be uneventful, when, on the ninth day, the doctor called me up by telephone and stated that the boy complained of a terrific headache. I saw the boy and diagnosed meningitis. In seventy-two hours he had all the classical symptoms of a well developed meningitis. I had to keep him under the influence of morphin until the time of death, which occurred the fourteenth day after operation, following a massive hemorrhage from his left ear."

In an article recently published in the *New York Medical Journal*, Dr. Thomas J. Harris takes exception to this procedure on the ground that the Eustachian tube is an important part of the organ of hearing and that it should not be destroyed, but that its function

should be preserved whenever it is possible to do so. With this opinion I am in full accord, but it is worth while to consider whether in the class of cases with which we are dealing the Eustachian tube has any function which can be preserved, and whether it has not assumed a perverted and pathological function. The function of the Eustachian tube may be considered under two heads—ventilation and drainage. By ventilation we understand the free passage of air through the Eustachian tube so as to maintain an equality of air-pressure on both sides of the drum membrane, in order that it may vibrate in unison with the vibrations of sound. Now a drum membrane which is perforated cannot respond to sound vibrations brought to it from the air, for the resonance of the drum depends upon the shape of the membrane as well as upon its tension as regulated by the tensor tympani muscle. When there is a perforation which cannot be closed, the shape of the membrane has been destroyed, and when suppuration has existed for a long time the thickenings and cicatricial contractures in the mucous membrane of the middle-ear, and in the ossicular chain and its muscles and tendons, will prevent such regulation. In other words, the remnant of the drum membrane is no longer a vibrating organ capable of transmitting sound from the external air to the fluid of the labyrinth. Even if it *could* vibrate, the equality of air-pressure on its two sides would be much more easily preserved through the perforation than through the Eustachian tube. The ventilating function of the Eustachian tube is therefore no longer useful.

The second function of the tube is drainage. In the perfectly healthy ear only the bony part of the tube is permanently open, the cartilaginous portion being normally closed and drainage of the small quantity of mucus secreted in the middle-ear is carried off through the tube by the action of cilia, which cover the surface of the mucous membrane of the normal cartilaginous tube. In chronic suppurative processes the cilia are destroyed and they can never be restored even when the suppuration ceases. Now the activity of the tube as an organ of drainage presupposes the passage of the aural secretion through its lumen. The lumen of the bony tube at its narrowest point, the isthmus, is one and one-half mm.; the lumen of the external auditory canal is about six mm. The passage of fluids through tubes depends upon the area of the cross section of the tubes. As the isthmus has one-quarter the diameter of the external auditory canal, the area of its cross section is one-sixteenth as great. The fluid would, therefore, meet with sixteen times as much resistance at the isthmus of the tube as it would in the external auditory canal. Now the fluid is so thick and its surface ten-

sion is so high that it will frequently refuse to flow out of the external auditory canal. It has only one-sixteenth as much chance to get through the isthmus and it is a law of physics that fluids will always follow the direction of least resistance. Even if it were possible for the secretion to flow through the isthmus, it would then meet with the resistance offered by the closed cartilaginous portion of the tube, and anyone who has syringed a suppurating ear knows that it is only when a considerable amount of pressure is used that any water (which is a much thinner and less viscid fluid than the aural secretion) can be driven through the tube into the throat. In short, in the presence of a perforation in the drum membrane, the drainage of secretion from the ear into the throat is a physical impossibility. The fact that in these cases a drop of secretion can frequently be seen in the pharyngeal mouth of the tube through the naso-pharyngoscope has been *wrongly* interpreted as indicating drainage from the ear; for this drop of secretion did not come down from the ear into the throat, but on the contrary, it is on its way to be driven from the throat into the ear. Furthermore, the idea of preserving the Eustachian tube as a drainage tube is a logical absurdity, for what is there to be drained away? If there is secretion in the middle-ear which requires a drain-pipe to carry it off, then the ear has not been cured, and if the ear has been cured, it is dry, absolutely and permanently dry, and there is no need for a drain-pipe.

We therefore see that in the conditions under consideration, both functions of the Eustachian tube have been permanently abrogated and can never be restored to it.

Whatever objections there may be to the closure of the Eustachian tube through the intact external auditory canal by the method under consideration, these same objections must also hold against the closure of the tube in the radical operation, for the method by which the closure is effected is the same in both cases, namely: the removal of the mucous membrane from the tube and its closure by granulation and cicatrization.

On the other hand, in the presence of a perforated drum membrane, the Eustachian tube has assumed a perverted function, for an intact drum membrane prevents the passage of air-currents through the tube, and it has been found by experiment both on the cadaver and the living that, without excessive pressure, it is impossible to force fluids through the Eustachian tube into the middle-ear. If this were not so, everybody would have an otitis media every time he blew his nose or sneezed.

When the drum membrane is perforated and its resistance is lost, it takes but a slight excess of pressure to force air through the tube and to propel particles of mucus bodily through the tube into the ear, a fact to which patients suffering from chronic aural suppuration have become so accustomed that they do not realize it until their attention is called to it.

It seems to me hardly necessary to repeat before this audience the well-known fact that suppuration of the ear *follows* infection of the naso-pharynx, and there is no one here who would assert that the aural suppuration is the primary factor and that the naso-pharynx has become diseased because the ear is draining into it. On the contrary, we are all familiar with the fact that a patient with a chronic aural suppuration is continually blowing his nose into his ears. It must, therefore, be accepted as true that instead of being a drainage tube, the Eustachian tube has become perverted into an avenue for the constant re-infection of the middle-ear, and that the closure of this avenue of infection has become imperative.

It is not an accidental coincidence that the men who first tried to close the Eustachian tube were those otologists who were most insistent upon the radical exposure of the diseased area in the middle-ear and its accessory cavities. For it was the radical otological surgeon who first discovered the fact that after he *had* thoroughly removed all the diseased tissue from the middle-ear, and converted the entire seat of the disease into a single, open wound, that he had not done enough, and that his cases did not heal in more than a small percentage; for the wound, however clean it might have been at the close of the operation, invariably became reinfected through the Eustachian tube. He therefore devised various methods of closing the tube. Some surgeons made a flap of mucous membrane from the mouth of the tube; others used the remnant of the drum membrane for this purpose; some devised curettes to remove the mucous membrane from the tube and others used burrs and reamers to ream out the tube with the same object in view; some surgeons used a chip of bone, which they removed from the cortex, as a plug which they drove down into the tube and some used a plug of ivory for the same purpose.

We see, therefore, that the necessity of closing the tube was first recognized by those surgeons who were most thorough in the removal of all the diseased tissue.

If the closure of the tube is necessary to secure healing when the entire diseased area has been converted into a single, smooth, shallow wound, how much less possible is it for nature to effect the healing of such a complicated series of passages as the middle-ear,

when the source of infection remains undisturbed and when fresh infection is being constantly added to that which already exists in the ear?

I cannot see, therefore, how we can escape the conclusion that inasmuch as the Eustachian tube has permanently lost its function, its closure is harmless; and, inasmuch as it assumes a perverted or pathological function, its patency is detrimental, and its closure has become a therapeutic necessity.

That it is possible to close the Eustachian tube by the technic and with the instruments described by me is attested by the fact that of the 735 cases here reported, 609, or 83 per cent have actually been closed.

Many of the surgeons who have responded to this investigation stated that they found these particular instruments, because of their shape and handiness, the most efficient for the curettement of the tube in the radical operation. Naturally, when the middle-ear cavity has been entirely exposed by this procedure, the surgeon's hand is guided not only by the sense of touch, but by the sight also, so that the management of the instrument is much easier under these circumstances. When the curette is used through the intact auditory canal, the operator is guided by the sense of touch only, and consequently the efficient use of the instrument requires more practice and experience. I believe that it is possible for any otologist to acquire sufficient skill to close the tube after the first curetting in practically all of the cases, so that it should not be necessary to curette more than once. Only 266 cases, or 36 per cent were closed after the first curetting in this series, while two or more curettings were needed in 244 cases. The fact also that the tube reopened in 139 cases, after it had apparently been closed, indicates that the curettement was insufficient, for if the mucous membrane is not removed from the entire circumference of the isthmus, atresia will follow. As the tube is often angular in cross section this is not always easy.

When this instrument was first devised about ten years ago, I stood in great awe of the danger of injuring the carotid artery, and took special pains to so construct the instrument as to ensure its safety as well as its efficiency, so that the operator could not lose control of it and plunge it through the bone. These precautions have apparently been well advised, for in not a single instance was the carotid artery injured; for there was no fatal hemorrhage at the time of operation in any case. In fact, hemorrhage sufficiently profuse to be designated as severe was reported in only 26,

or 3.6 per cent of the cases. Many of these cases were operated upon under general anesthesia, under which condition hemorrhage from the mucous membrane of any part of the head is always more severe; when done under local anesthesia, the addition of adrenalin usually prevents all hemorrhage.

On account of the fact that the capsule of the labyrinth constitutes the posterior wall of the tube, and that in curetting the tube we are removing the mucous membrane from the surface of the labyrinth capsule, the effect of this operation upon the hearing and upon the tinnitus, when this symptom is present, is of special interest. The hearing was reported upon in 564 cases, of which in 258, or 46 per cent, the hearing is reported as improved; in 281 cases, 50 per cent, as unimproved, and in 25 cases, or 4 per cent, as having been made worse. Now the total percentage of cases in which the suppuration was cured was 51 per cent; the total percentage of cases in which the hearing was improved was 46 per cent, so that of every 51 cases, in which the suppuration was cured, the hearing was improved in 46, i. e., in 90 per cent of the cured cases. In contrast to the behavior of the hearing after the radical operation, these figures need no comment.

The fact that in only 4 per cent of all cases was the hearing made worse is rather surprising, because when any operative procedure is undertaken in chronic aural suppuration, which does not lead to a cure, the hearing may well be expected to be made worse by the procedure.

Tinnitus was reported as having been present in 365 cases and of these, the tinnitus is reported as having been lessened in 189, or 52 per cent of the cases; unchanged in 159, or 43 per cent of the cases and made worse in 17, or 5 per cent of the cases. It is evident, therefore, that improvement in tinnitus also followed in as many cases as were cured of the suppuration, and, that it was not increased by this operative procedure, except in an insignificant percentage of the cases, is equally surprising as in the case of the hearing. Perhaps this may be explained by the behavior of those cases in which the suppuration was not cured, for more than half of these are reported as having been improved, that is to say, the suppuration was lessened.

We may, therefore, sum up the effect of this operation upon the suppurating ear by the statement that half of the cases are cured with an improvement in the hearing and a diminution of the tinnitus, and that in the cases that were not cured, half of them had the suppuration lessened.

It is therefore evident that the closure of the tube has a decidedly beneficial effect upon the suppuration, upon the tinnitus, and upon the auditory function.

This conclusion is of special interest to the otologist who desires to increase the percentage of his cures from the radical operation; for, of the cases which were not cured by curetting the tube, 70 were subjected subsequently to radical operation, and the result reported in 68. Of these 60, or 88 per cent, were reported as having been cured. This percentage of cures from the radical operation is much higher than the average otologist can show, and I believe that this unusually high percentage of cures was due to the fact that in these cases the suppuration was diminished and the entire condition of the ear improved by the preceding curettement of the tube.

To those who control large numbers of cases in hospital and dispensary practice, I should say that this procedure is one which can suitably be carried out in dispensary practice and under local anesthesia, and that this should be done in every case; that only those cases which, after a sufficient length of time have not healed should be submitted to more radical procedures. Not only will the number of cases requiring radical operation be diminished thereby, but the percentage of cures of those that are radically operated will be appreciably raised.

This collective investigation therefore justifies the following position:

Whatever method we adopt to secure the healing of the diseased middle-ear cavities, whether we allow nature to effect the healing unaided, whether we stimulate the efforts of nature by the administration of vaccines, whether we make nature's work easier by the removal of some of the diseased parts by minor surgery, or whether we make her work easiest of all by radically removing all diseased tissue, in any event, we must in every case prevent the reinfection of the diseased area by closing the avenue of infection, the Eustachian tube.

Based upon these figures, we may draw the following conclusions:

1. That closure of the Eustachian tube is harmless because it does not cause the loss of any function which has not already been permanently destroyed.
2. That it is a valuable therapeutic agent because by it alone half of the cases are cured and the rest so improved that it enables the radical operation to cure most of them.
3. That it is imperative, not only because the tube has assumed a perverted or pathological function, but because the only other re-

source which is open to the patient is a radical operation, in which case the tube must be closed anyway.

4. That every patient should be given the benefit of this procedure, not only because the chances of cure are sufficiently high, but also because if cured thereby the hearing will not only be preserved, but improved.

5. I believe that the figures here presented also justify me in making the statement that on account of the difference in the effect upon the hearing, the radical operation should be regarded as unjustifiable in any case where there is useful hearing left until a thorough trial has been given to the closure of the tube alone through the intact auditory passages.

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Auricular Hematidrosis. E. GUARNACCIA and V. SBORNI, *Arch. ital. di Otol., Rinol. e Laryngol.*, V. 27, No. 3, 1915.

True hematidrosis is a localized transcutaneous hemorrhage taking place through the intact skin. It usually occurs in hysterical patients and seems to stand in relationship to vicarious menstruation in general. While hematidrosis may occur in various localities (finger-tips, forehead, nose), the auricular localization is extremely rare. Often the hemorrhage may be symmetrical (as in the case reported by the authors), and the intervals of recurrence are irregular. Hematidrosis has not been observed in the male sex. Its relationship to menstruation is well shown by Charvanne's series of 37 cases of otorrhagia, of which only 7 were independent of the menstrual function. Emotional disturbances are usually the provocative factors.

The prognosis is always benign, even though the hemorrhage is frequent and abundant (as in the authors' case).

The hemorrhage ceases spontaneously. Treatment should be directed between attacks to the underlying hemopathic condition.

Ed.